

**INDIA-AFRICA COOPERATION AND INTERNATIONAL
STUDENT MIGRATION TO INDIAN HIGHER EDUCATION
INSTITUTIONS: POLICY INITIATIVES, CHALLENGES, AND
RECOMMENDATIONS**

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Abstract:

India and African countries share a long history of cooperation. Recent India's engagement with African countries is evidenced by the opening of new Indian Missions and consulates in eighteen African countries in 2018. India's partnership with African countries has been built on the solid foundation of South-South Cooperation. Capacity building to the African youth and labour force through relevant education policy initiatives and infrastructural development have been essential among many strands of South-South Cooperation. This study aims to examine the development partnership and educational policy initiatives implemented by the Indian government in facilitating African students' mobility to Indian higher education institutions (IHEIs), establish the challenges faced by African students, and recommend interventions to bolster the development partnership between India and African counterparts through capacity building of the African youth. Using a quantitative research design through purposive sampling, a questionnaire was administered to 87 African students through the Kobo data collection tool. Secondary data were gathered from online sources, virtual archives, and libraries. Based on the study's findings, a notable majority of 84% of the respondents are enrolled in the Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR) scholarship program, while the remaining 16% are under other various programs. Scholarship award significantly facilitated their mobility to IHEIs. Language barrier and delayed stipend disbursement emerged as major concerns among students. The primary significance of these findings lies in their contribution to a deeper understanding of the dynamics of India-Africa

educational bilateral cooperation and identifying areas requiring improvement to enhance its effectiveness and mutual benefits.

Keyword: Mobility, India-Africa Cooperation, International Student Migration, Indian Higher Education Institutions

1. Introduction

India-Africa cooperation is more prevalent in contemporary political discourses. It can be traced back to the trade interaction between 'India and the Kingdom of Aksum.'. These trade relations are suggested to have started in the first century, and Africans have likely lived in India since the eighth century AD (Lavakare & Powar, 2013). With this shared history of trade, colonialism, and a unified vision of developing together under the banner of South-South cooperation, long ago, Indian traders continually looked further past the west of the Arabian Sea, especially to Zanzibar for rhino horns, spices, palm oil, gold, and copper as well as seeking lucrative markets for their goods (Civildaily, 2022). In the medieval period, as cited by Marco Polo, the Gujarati and Saurashtrian traders played a crucial role in the African east coast and used the Indian system of weights and measures and cowries as currency in the area (Civildaily, 2022). In their quest to achieve greater autonomy and ensure that the agenda of the global south is prioritised, India and African countries have had a long history of partnership through coordinating their views and efforts in institutions of global governance and multilateral forums (Viswanathan & Mishra, 2019). India-Africa trade patterns and relations changed when traders and other enslaved Indians, as well as indentured red labourers, gradually settled in the African continent, mainly in the Eastern Africa region (Civildaily, 2022). The development collaboration between India and African partners is organised in a unique three-tiered structure that includes bilateral, regional, and pan-African cooperation (Malyan & Jindal, 2014). In the spirit of developing together as equals, India and African countries share a rich history of cultural, economic, and political engagements (Viswanathan & Mishra, 2019). With their opposition to colonialism, India and African countries have had a long relationship reinforced by Jawaharlal Nehru, then India's Foreign Affairs Minister, who considered relationships with African countries important (Sharma, 2008). Malyan and Jindal (2014) state that the struggle against apartheid and colonialism is the most contemporary engagement between the two regions. Gandhi, an architect of the philosophy of 'Satyagraha,' used the

strategy in South Africa to awaken the oppressed Africans and Indians to defend and fight for a dignified life and their freedom (Sharma, 2007). In contemporary times, India-Africa cooperation has been a legitimate mutualistic affair with shared dreams, according to former vice president Hamid Ansari (Civildaily, 2022). In July 2008, on his official visit to the African continent, The Indian Prime Minister, while addressing the Ugandan parliament in Kampala, pronounced that the African continent is India's top priority and that India will continue intensifying and deepening engagement with Africa (Viswanathan & Mishra, 2019). The partnerships between the Indian subcontinent and African countries are increasing and developing in the current century, drawing them together with a shared goal pegged on fraternity and equality (Krishna, 2010) with the institutionalisation of India-Africa relations through the India-Africa Forum Summit 2008 and three other subsequent summits offers a basic framework for South-South cooperation (Civildaily, 2022). To expand knowledge on India-Africa cooperation, more so in the educational sector, this study examined the development partnership and educational policy initiatives implemented by the Indian government in facilitating African students' capacity-building process and mobility to Indian higher education institutions. It equally establishes the challenges faced by African students in Indian higher education institutions due to existing policy gaps. It suggests addressing the gaps and strengthening bilateral education cooperation between India and Africa.

2. Literature Review

India's objective to build up South-South Cooperation and raise mutual economic benefits to the partners through the promotion of capacity-building programs, trade, and investment is not developed as a donor-recipient relationship (Malyan & Jindal, 2014). African countries and India are developing in politics, economics, and population (Krishna, 2010). Correspondingly, India has had a strong feeling and motivation toward African countries to see Africa and herself advance together. In the words of Sharma (2007), India and African countries have always had a respectful and equitable relationship that has never involved any form of exploitation. Both sides benefit from a young population, rapidly expanding economies, and abundant natural resources, which intrigues and inspires jealousy in the rest of the globe (Kumar, 2022).

Trade Relations

India and the African continent have had trade relations for a long time. As mentioned earlier in this paper, these trade partnerships can be traced back to the trade interaction between 'India and the Kingdom of Aksum,' which is believed to have started in the first century. Africans have likely lived in India since the eighth century AD (Lavakare & Powar, 2013). With the launch of India's duty-free tariff policy for developing countries in 2008, Thirty-three African countries have benefited from the plan (Singh, 2022). India's structured engagement with African countries under the banner of three editions of the India Africa Forum Summit (IAFS) in 2008, 2011, and 2015 has contributed to a total number of 29 visits of the president, vice president, and prime minister to African countries since 2014 (Viswanathan & Mishra, 2019). From 2019 to 2020, commerce between India and Africa increased to almost 66.7 billion dollars. Africa accounts for 'around 8% of Indian' imports, whereas India accounts for about 9% of African imports (Kumar, 2022).

Geostrategic and Security relations

The African continent has been strategically important to the Indian subcontinent. Due to its geostrategic location in India, the African continent, especially the Horn of Africa and the Sub-Saharan regions, plays a vital role in India's territorial security (Civildaily, 2022). In her vision and motivation to see peace in the African continent, in his speech to the Ugandan Parliament during his state visit to the country, the Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi stated that India has historically taken part in almost all peacekeeping missions in Africa with over 6,000 Indians soldiers serving in five peacekeeping operations in Africa (Viswanathan & Mishra, 2019).

Political and Diplomatic relations

India and African countries share a lot in their political and diplomatic relations. Notably, it is recorded that around 1.5 million Africans are living in India now, spread out across the whole nation (Gupta, 2023). Similarly, many Indians live in African countries. It is believed that the Indian diaspora in Africa moved there as 'colonial indentured' workers, with Africa playing a significant role in India's foreign policy (Malik, 2020). India's involvement in the affairs of many African countries gives her a platform to show her soft and hard power to the African continent, which is vital in India's drive to gain a permanent seat in the United Nations Security Council (Civildaily, 2022).

Agriculture and Energy Partnerships

India and Africa's continent had partnerships in agriculture, food, and energy, among many government and private sectors. The agricultural partnership between African countries and India has been enhanced by the launch of incubation centers and the promotion of agribusiness in Africa. (Viswanathan & Mishra, 2019). Furthermore, India and Africa partner in solar energy development, climate change engagements, information technology, and disaster relief, among many areas of cooperation (Civildaily, 2022). With Africa's natural resource endowment, the Indian subcontinent has always had a keen eye on Africa's great source of energy reserves (Sharma, 2007). African countries are essential partners in addressing India's food security due to their sufficient arable land and help to diversify India's energy sources, as mentioned in India's Integrated Energy Policy objectives (Civildaily, 2022).

Education Relations

International Student Migration has been at the center point in India, of which the majority come to India for higher education. India's cooperation with African partners has been built on the solid foundation of South-South Cooperation. Capacity building and infrastructural development have been essential strands of South-South Cooperation, which is evident in India's assistance to the youth of African countries in pursuing higher education in India. Besides, India has always sought to strengthen its multifaceted connection with African countries, including capacity-building programs for local youth, the continent's largest employer and the fourth-largest investor (India-Africa Higher Education and Skill Development Summit, 2019).

With her vision of developing together and mutual benefit, Indian and African countries' collaboration, primarily in capacity building, is targeted to benefit the African youth and the Indian society. According to UGC Chairman Mamidala Jagadesh Kumar, admitting international students will help institutions generate internal resources through tuition fees that can then be used to improve the infrastructure and further attract more international students (Niazi, 2022). It is also important to

note that many Africans who went to India to study occupied high-ranking posts after returning home, acting as India's education institution's agents in those nations (Lavakare & Powar, 2013).

As a result of its swift economic developments, improved health and educational standards, increased gender parity, and growing infrastructure and connections, India and African countries' relationships have not escaped competition and interference from other interested parties. The newly emerging political powers, particularly Indian neighbours in the Asian continent, including but not limited to China, Japan, Singapore, and Malaysia, are also stepping up their presence in the African continent (Viswanathan & Mishra, 2019).

3. Materials and Methods

This study adopted quantitative research with some qualitative elements of the survey tool used. Quantitative research was used to assess Indian government policies facilitating African students' mobility to Indian higher education, identify challenges faced by African students, and propose interventions. Data was collected through primary and secondary sources. Primary data was gathered through an online survey sent to African international students in Indian higher education institutions. Secondary data were gathered from journal articles, books, newspapers, magazines, and reports accessed through online sources, virtual archives, and libraries. Purposive sampling was used to choose only African international students who are purposely in India for their studies and still hold valid education visas. With a sample size of 110 students, the researchers received 87 responses. The quantitative data was compiled and analysed using Excel and presented as tables, graphs, and charts. The results were interpreted according to the concepts of the study. Information from the respondents was treated with utmost confidentiality as per the ethical requirements of social science research.

4. Results

In this section, the authors present findings from the interview data collected from 87 respondents regarding the educational programs available for African international students in Indian higher education institutions. Their gender, age, and the region of Africa they hail from are presented in this section. The existing challenges and policy gaps,

together with suggestions to address the gaps and eventually strengthen India-Africa education bilateral cooperation, are equally presented.

4.1 Distribution of respondents according to gender and age

Figure 1: Distribution of gender by age: Source: Original Data (2024)

Figure 1 shows the respondent's uptake of capacity-building opportunities according to their age and gender. It illustrates that the 26-30 years and below 25 years age set, respectively, are the dominant group. More males form the large portion of the age groups 31-35 years and above 35 years old, respectively. This coincides with the policy where ICCR has put an age cap on the scholarship opportunities given to African students and scholars for their capacity-building programs.

4.2 Distribution of respondents according to gender and the region of African

Figure 2: Distribution of gender and the region of Africa: Source: Original Data (2024)

Figure 2 shows that most respondents hail from the Eastern part of Africa. No female respondents are shown in the northern and central parts of the African continent. This coincides with our literature that India-Africa relations started with trade in the kingdom of Aksum, located in northern Ethiopia and Zanzibar, under the United Republic of Tanzania, which both fall under the Eastern Africa region. Since the northern part of Africa is a Muslim-dominated region, most females are reserved to move outside their countries. Few who might get an opportunity to seek education outside their countries tend to settle in other West Asian countries that are Arab-dominated. Central parts of Africa have been experiencing political instability and insecurities that do not favour the female gender to manoeuvre and seek opportunities away from their home country.

4.3 Education Policy Initiatives (Schemes) Against the African Region

Figure 3: The distribution of the educational schemes and region: Source: Original Data (2024)

Figure 3 shows the distribution of the schemes (initiatives) under which respondents are enrolled in Indian higher education institutions according to their regions. Most respondents from East African and South African regions take a significant share of the initiatives under the ICCR. Almost all the respondents who come from the Central African region are self-sponsored.

4.4 Education Funding Initiatives (Schemes)

Figure 4: Distribution of respondents by funding initiative: Source: Original Data (2024)

A more significant portion of 84% of the respondents are enrolled under the ICCR scholarship program, with the remaining 16% falling under study in India, self-sponsored, and other programs. This shows that most African students are taking advantage of the scholarship opportunities offered by the Indian government through ICCR.

4.5 Contributing factors to the mobility of African international students to Indian higher education institutions (HEIs)

Table 1: Contributing factors to the mobility of African students to Indian HEIs

Contributing factor	Frequency of the respondents	Percentage
Scholarship award	76	87.4
Cultural exchange program	2	2.3
Study visa	2	2.3
Low cost of education	3	3.4
Educational grants	3	3.4
Reserved seat at the university	1	1.2

Source: Original Data (2024)

The results in Table 1 show that almost all respondents (87.4%) record that the scholarship award is the main contributor to their mobility to Indian higher education institutions. The remaining few (12.6%) record cultural exchange programs, study visas, low-cost education, education grants, and reserved seats at Indian education institutions as the main reasons for their mobility to India.

4.6 Challenges faced by African international students in Indian

Figure 5: Challenges of African students in India: Source: Original Data (2024)

Figure 5 shows that most respondents recorded delays in student allowances and language barrier as the most significant challenges affecting their stay in India. Language barrier and delayed stipends were the major problems reported among students at 62% and 55%, respectively. The least recorded racial profiling is a significant challenge. This shows that Indian society is diverse and receptive to visitors.

4.7 Merits of Staying in India

Table 2: Merits of Staying in India

Merits of staying in India	Frequency of the respondents	Percentage
Low cost of leaving	57	51.82
Culture	41	37.27
Quality of education	38	34.55

Food	33	30
Reputable universities	24	21.82
Others	9	8.18
Local languages	6	5.45

Source: Original Data (2024)

The low cost of living and culture were the primary merits for studying in India, with 51.83% and 37.27% of respondents, respectively (Table 2). This was followed by more than one-third of the respondents, 34.55% and 30%, indicating that the quality of education and food in India was the merits of studying there. A little over 20% of the respondents also cited India's reputable universities as their main reason for studying there.

5. Discussions

Overview of Implemented Policy Programs

The literature shows that the Indian government has implemented several policy initiatives through the concerned departments. This has facilitated the mobility of African international students to Indian higher education institutions. This study reveals that several African international students migrate to Indian higher education institutions to benefit from the scholarship scheme offered by the Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR). Another contributing factor to the mobility of African international students to Indian higher educational institutions is the educational grants offered by wide-ranging organisations in India. Affordable universities and college fees are among the main reasons students find self-financing enticing in Indian higher education institutions. Prestigious government institutions like the IITs and IIMs are among the main contributing factors to student migration to Indian higher education institutions. Indian higher education institutions have used their alums as their ambassadors to market their institutions on the African continent. Easy and efficient education visa acquisition is one of the many successful policy initiatives undertaken by the Indian government through their foreign embassies and consulates abroad. Reservation of seats for African international students in Indian higher education institutions is an essential factor in promoting India as one of the leading education destinations globally.

Policy Initiatives

Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR) and Scholarships Awards

Culture plays a vital role as it identifies the traditions, beliefs, and customs of a people in the society. As part of the commitment to showcasing its culture, India offers capacity-building programs for the labour force, mainly from the African continent, through ICCR and other scholarship schemes. The Indian government has remarked that there are more opportunities to attract foreign scholars and students to its higher education institutions, which are increasingly dedicated to extending their worldwide reach (Niazi, 2022). Our study finds that a more significant portion of 84% of the respondents are enrolled in a culturally spearheaded program under ICCR. This finding coincides with Malyan & Jindal's statement that India has had a routine of offering scholarship opportunities in graduate and postgraduate courses encompassing a wide range of disciplines to developing countries, especially in Africa, through the Indian Council for Cultural Relations (Malyan & Jindal, 2014). Moreover, the Ministry of External Affairs, India, through the ICCR, offers various cultural events that happen all year in India as part of the cultural exchange, allowing African international students to immerse themselves into the Indian culture by meeting new people and learning about Indian culture (Gupta, 2023). However, Sharma (2008) states that the goal of the internationalisation of education should not be seen as interfering with a nation's moral standards but should be geared towards strengthening relations among students.

The 'Study in India' Initiative and Education Grants

Among many areas of partnerships, education cooperation in capacity building is one of the crucial areas of India and African countries' relations. India has provided educational support to eligible international students under the "Study in India Programme" and educational grants through its advanced and prestigious higher education institutions like the Indian Institute of Management (IIM) and the Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) (Gupta, 2023). Educational grants, which are need-based programmes, provide full or partial student support under specific criteria. Our findings depict that 7%, slightly less than one-tenth of the total respondents, joined HEIs through the support of the "Study in India Programme" and other educational grants. This finding shows that many educational study opportunities are populated by the scholarships awarded through ICCR.

Technical Exchange Programs and Reserved Seats

The Indian government has approved many vital policies related to capacity-building programs and the development of human resources, especially for African youth and professionals (Krishna, 2010). The introduced programs are geared towards exchanging ideas, sharing expertise, and acquiring knowledge among officials and youth in these two great regions. Capacity building and training programs under Indian Technical and Economic Cooperation (ITEC); Lines of Credit (LOC) or concessional loans and grant assistance; trade; and investments have been the four main pillars of India's development partnership approach to African countries (Viswanathan & Mishra, 2019). The most notable initiatives in this category are ITEC courses, which provide fully-funded on-campus ITEC courses at prestigious higher education and training institutions spread all over India (ITEC, 2023). Our results show that a meagre 3% of the total respondents reported being enrolled in technical exchange programs and reserved seat opportunities in India's higher education institutions. This finding shows that the UGC's 15% vacancies as supernumerary seats for international students in academic institutions, according to Sharma (2008), are not well taken by international students.

Study Visas and Other Facilitating Policies

In order to facilitate the hassle-free acquisition of education and other related visas, the Indian government, through the ministry concerned, has established specialised visa centers across the African continent (Gupta, 2023). With these straightforward and customer-friendly policies, getting an Indian education visa is manageable with proper documentation. Our findings show that just slightly above 2% of respondents chose to take up Indian study opportunities because of the easy visa acquisition process. This coincides with the Lavakare & Powar (2013) statement that it is difficult to attain an Indian visa. Contrary to Lavakare and Powar's claim that Indian education is challenging, I state that as a beneficiary, it is easy to get an Indian education visa due to flexible policies. For example, the Indian High Commission in Nairobi, Kenya, exempts students admitted under programs offered through ICCR from appearing for visa interview meetings. They are only required to complete and submit their application form with the attached required documents. The process is fast, and it is being fast-tracked by the embassy staff, making acquiring Indian education visas effortless.

Low Cost of Education and Self-sponsorship

India's interactions with the African continent emphasise its core capabilities based on mutual agreement. Capacity building and skill development for human resources is a critical component of India-Africa bilateral relations (Kumar, 2022). (Lavakare & Powar, 2013) opine that India has better and more affordable higher education institutions, making it attainable for self-sponsored African students. Moreover, Dixon (2006) opines that in India, private schools are affordable, with some providing concessionary seats and even free education. Our findings show that 6% of the respondents reported being on self-sponsored programs in India HEIs, slightly lower than those who reported benefitting from the study India education program.

Challenges

In her dream to grow with other developing states, mainly in the African continent, India has implemented many vital policies to provide capacity-building programmes to African students within and outside the country. With the vision of South-South cooperation, India joined its Western colleagues in a small way by offering scholarship opportunities and reserved seats in its HEIs to youths and other labour forces from the global south, particularly in the African continent (Lavakare & Powar, 2013). Mullen D & Arora (2016) state that Indo-Africa cooperation focuses on the capacity building of the African youth and the labour force, technological initiatives, development cooperation, and economic and trade relationships. Notwithstanding, the Indian government must be aware of the policy gaps that might affect India's educational cooperation with its African partners through its specific HEIs. Our study found gaps in capacity building and training for the African youth and the labour force.

Quality Education

Ensuring that quality education is offered to the masses is one of the critical policies that the Indian government aims to fulfil. Some Indian higher educational institutions are still grappling with offering quality and reputable education. Our study found that 22 responses recorded that compromised quality education is a challenge in Indian higher education institutions, which is slightly above institutional bottlenecks and racial profiling. This concurs with Subrahmanyam Jaishankar, the country's minister of external affairs, statement that sometimes, graduates from

Indian higher education institutions were not able to get job opportunities back in their countries after graduation because of the poor quality of their degrees that were attained from Indian universities and colleges and this reduced the mobility of African international students to Indian and other Asian nations higher education institutions (Waruru, 2022). Many African international students travel to India through agencies and fall for false and exaggerated representations of specific prestigious colleges, which compromise the quality of education they acquire.

Financial Support Delays

Delayed African international students' educational and financial support is worrying, and students and scholars find it challenging to have a decent living with the delay of their stipend. This study reveals that 55 of the responses, the second highest language barrier, reported that financial delays are a significant issue affecting their life in India. This even applies to the provision of return air tickets to their countries after completing their programs, and their visas expire. This finding concurs with the findings of Hyams-Ssekasi et al. (2014) on African postgraduate students' encounters in their quest for international education in the United Kingdom. In this study, nearly all respondents cited financial uncertainties as the main challenge.

Language barrier

Communication is the lifeline of any relationship. African students use English as a communication language, while most Indians prefer their local dialect to English as a language of communication. Most state higher education institutions use their local languages as a medium of instruction. This discrepancy in language makes the visitors and the non-locals alike face challenges in communication and, eventually, affects their peaceful coexistence and education performance. Our findings show that 62 respondents with the highest recorded responses feel that the language barrier is a significant problem they face in Indian society. These findings are consistent with those of Yoganandan (2015), wherein the author highlighted language barriers as a significant challenge international students face, hindering their ability to integrate effectively into new societies.

Institutional bottlenecks

The primary reason for African international students' mobility to Indian higher education institutions is to seek capacity-building and training

courses. In their quest for higher education, many students who come to India are from African states, Caribbean Island states, Australia and many other countries within and outside the Asian continent (Sharma, 2008). Gribble (2008) opines that, along with improved research capability and better employment opportunities, many international students consider international education an avenue to permanent residency in countries with improved living standards. For the objectives of these international students to be met, there must be proper and efficient support in all administrative processes of the universities and colleges they have enrolled in. (Gribble, 2008) argues that the chief impediment to many third-world countries is to formulate policies which facilitate and take full advantage of opportunities for increased student mobility and limit the challenges associated with the lack of such policies. Their adaptation process will also depend on how the processes integrate them into Indian society. Some African international students face challenges associated with institutional bottlenecks, unfair treatment, and harassment in acquiring crucial documents. Our findings reveal that institutional bottlenecks are a significant challenge for African international students. Nineteen responses, the fourth highest number of responses below the language barrier, delayed allowances, and culture shock, confirmed that institutional bottlenecks are a challenge affecting them.

Cultural barrier

African international students come from different cultural backgrounds, making it difficult for them to adopt the Indian culture with ease. These students have often faced cultural stress, with some getting depression. Culture is a multifaceted concept, including food, language, dress, customs, and traditions. Since African international students have different food habits and food types, it is challenging to adapt to the Indian food culture, affecting their health and academic performance. Our findings reveal that 35 out of the total responses, the third highest above language barrier and delayed allowances, documented that cultural shock is a real issue affecting them. This finding agrees with a statement that communication barriers, unavailability of native food, and cultural obstacles affect African international students, especially at the beginning of their stay in India (Yoganandan, 2015). In addition, Galloway and Jenkins (2005, as cited in Wu et al. 2015) opine that language is one of the most significant academic challenges preventing international students from adjusting well, which is a recipe of culture.

Racial Profiling and harassment

Racial prejudice is alive in all parts of the world. Our findings reveal that 13 respondents' responses were the least documented. Despite it being an issue to deal with, racial profiling and harassment are not a significant issue. This contradicts Mishra's (2020) account, 'The question of racial prejudice and biases has once again come to the forefront. Racial bias is the most unfortunate challenge facing Africans in India'.

6. Recommendations

To address the identified policy gaps and enhance India-Africa education bilateral cooperation, several recommendations are proposed:

Clear, Authentic, and Accessible Information: Improve the dissemination of information regarding educational policies, admission procedures, available scholarships, and support services for African students. This can be achieved through authentic online portals, informative brochures, and regular webinars targeting African countries. One of our respondents suggested that:

“The government, through the agencies in charge of Scholarships, should provide medical insurance. Scholarships, including ICCR, provide medical insurance for Students admitted to Indian higher education institutions. The government of India should crack down on institutions that promise African students full scholarships on their websites and through their agents, yet they do not offer any scholarships. The institutions should be forced to fully disclose the terms and conditions of their scholarships to the target audience” (SR -58).

While the University Grants Commission (UGC), India, must ensure that the contents of universities and colleges' websites are authentic, African international students must also do their due diligence by confirming the information received.

Cultural Orientation and Sensitization: Conduct orientation and cultural exchange programmes for incoming African students to help them adapt to India's new academic environment and societal norms. Similarly, awareness creation and sensitisation of Indian faculty and students about their African counterparts' diverse cultures and backgrounds ensure a more inclusive and harmonious learning atmosphere. A respondent gave a suggestion that:

“Preparing International students psychologically on the challenges they might face by informing them earlier” (SR - 5).

One more respondent recommended that:

“As much as India wants to preserve its culture, it is prudent they learn to accommodate other diversities, especially students from Africa; stipends are a means of survival for students and must be processed in time. India needs to provide internships to African students to nurture expertise; Acceptance is a key aspect to learning; the faculties should learn to acknowledge the presence of African students, especially in class delivery” (SR - 14).

It is upon the African international students who are the beneficiaries to uptake these opportunities and remain open-minded to benefit from the opportunities offered by these organisations.

Academic Support Services: Establish support systems within Indian higher education institutions that cater to the specific academic needs of African students. This could include psychological counselling, local language orientation classes, and other mentorship programs that may ensure a smoother learning experience. One of our respondents succinctly stated that:

“To provide optional classes for local language to foreign students for better communication with the local pupil” (SR - 12).

Another respondent suggested that:

“Institutions should plan to teach basic Hindi language during the start of the study for international students” (SR - 20).

These academic support services through cultural exchange programs support international students’ integration into Indian culture.

Networking Opportunities: Organize regular events, seminars, and conferences that bring together Indian and African students, academicians, and professionals to foster cross-cultural exchanges and create networking opportunities. One of our participants recorded that:

“Indians know nothing about Africa; they think they are better than Africans. It is time they recommend Indian cultural exchange so that they can travel and see the world” (SR - 34).

In order to enhance India's competitive advantage globally, she must build on experiences, ensure the safety of Africans studying and working in the country, and sensitise Indians about Africa to enhance mass connections between the two regions and make it flourish (Civildaily, 2022).

Institutional Partnerships: Internationalising India's higher education institution's curriculum and promoting English as a medium of instruction is necessary. Through relevant agencies, the government should encourage collaborations between Indian and African universities to facilitate faculty and student exchanges, joint research projects, and curriculum development. This can strengthen academic ties and promote mutual understanding between the two regions.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Implement a comprehensive monitoring and evaluation framework to assess the quality of education offered through the suitable medium of communication by the Indian higher education institutions and the effectiveness of existing policies and initiatives in supporting African students. Regular feedback from students and relevant stakeholders can aid in identifying areas for improvement and making necessary adjustments. One of our interview participants said that:

“Proper evaluation of universities by ICCR should be done” (SR - 17).

Finally, a proper and working regulatory framework should be used to monitor quality in Indian higher education institutions.

Government Support: Foster more robust governmental support and financial backing for educational initiatives aimed at African students. This can include payment of stipends on time, increased scholarship funding, more research grants, and infrastructure development in Indian universities. One of our respondents alluded to this by saying:

“Increase funding for international students” (SR - 34).

The departments concerned with the student's affairs should review and, if possible, increase their allowances. Students' stipends should also be released on time to avoid unnecessary suffering.

Unity of Purpose: African international students in India's HEIs should cooperate and align their individual goals with the group objectives. This will ensure solidarity among them and guarantee efficiency in their studies. They should embrace each other and labour to embrace the

Indian culture. A lot of emphasis and focus should be directed towards their education goals. One of our respondents stated that there should be; “Solidarity among students and support from concerned authorities” (SR - 15).

By incorporating these recommendations into the existing educational policy framework, the Indian government can create a more conducive and inclusive environment for African students studying in India. Simultaneously, such measures will strengthen India-Africa education bilateral cooperation, leading to meaningful academic and cultural exchanges and nurturing future leaders who will contribute to the progress and development of both regions.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study sheds light on the educational policy initiatives undertaken by the Indian government to foster capacity building and mobility for African students in Indian higher education institutions. It has provided valuable insights into the challenges faced by African students during their educational tours to India, primarily arising from existing policy gaps. The findings of this research contribute to a deeper understanding of the dynamics of India-Africa education bilateral cooperation and the areas that require improvement to make it more effective and mutually beneficial and fulfil the vision of south-south cooperation. This study highlights that while the Indian government has taken significant steps to attract African students and promote educational collaboration, specific policy gaps remain hindrances to a seamless experience for African students. These gaps range from administrative and logistical issues to cultural and social integration challenges, which have the potential to affect the overall academic and personal growth of the students. This study offers some suggestions and recommendations for implementation for India to achieve her vision of growing with other developing states, primarily in Africa, and attracting many students from the African continent.

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